

Synthesis and biological activity of some new 1,3-thiazolyl-6-bromoquinazolin-4(3H)ones

N. B. Patel* and J. N. Patel

Department of Chemistry, Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007, Gujarat, India

E-mail : drnavin@satyam.net.in

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Abstract : The title compound 1,3-thiazolyl-6-bromoquinazolin-4(3H)ones **5_{i-xv}** have been synthesized from the molecule 2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetic acid **1** through multi-step reaction sequence. The structures of new compounds have been confirmed by elemental analyses, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral data. All the compounds were evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Keywords : Quinazolin-4(3H)one, 1,3-thiazole, antibacterial, antifungal.

Introduction

Thiazole, a heterocyclic nucleus, played a pivotal role in the development of different medicinal important moiety. Thiazole antifungals are known as potent inhibitors of the cytochrome P450 monooxygenase in the process of fungal biosynthesis of ergosterol, which is an important constitution of fungal cell membrane¹. They are widely used as an accelerator in rubber vulcanization and as antioxidants^{2,3}. They are also reported to exhibit diverse biological activities, such as antibacterial⁴, antifungal⁵, antiviral⁶, antitubercular⁷, anti-inflammatory⁸, anticancer⁹, insecticidal¹⁰ and anticonvulsant.

Quinazolinones have been found to be endowed with a variety of biological activities such as CNS depressant¹¹, antihistaminic¹², anti-inflammatory¹³, antipyretic¹⁴, anticancer¹⁵, antihypertensive¹⁶, antibacterial¹⁷ and antifungal¹⁸ activities. In continuation of our studies on quinazolinone¹⁹⁻²³ derivatives, and in search of novel lead compounds associated with different biological activities, we have tempted to synthesize some new quinazolinone system consisting 2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetic acid at C-2 and 1,3-thiazolyl system at C-3 positions.

Results and discussion

Antimicrobial activity :

All the synthesized compounds were tested for their antibacterial and antifungal activity (MIC) *in vitro* by broth dilution method with two Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus*, *S. pyogenes* and two Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*, *P.*

aeruginosa and fungi *C. albicans*, *A. niger* and *A. clavatus* organisms taking gentamycin, ampicillin, chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin, norfloxacin, nystatin and greseofulvin as standard drugs.

Antibacterial and antifungal activity of 15 amide derivatives of substituted primary aromatic amines as an intermediate have been screened and compared with the final products, which shows that some of the amides presented very good activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria especially amide **vi** (R = 4-CH₃) and **viii** (R = 3-NO₂) showed good activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria respectively.

The screening results of compounds **5viii**, **xii** (R = 3-NO₂, 2-Cl, 4-NO₂) showed excellent activity against both Gram-negative bacteria. While compounds **5ix**, **xiii** (4-NO₂, 3,4-(Cl)₂) displayed excellent activity against Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and compound **5i** (R = 4-OCH₃) presented excellent activity against Gram-negative bacteria *P. aeruginosa*. While compounds **5x**, **xiv** (R = 4-OCH₃, 2,5-(Cl)₂) gave excellent activity against Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and compounds **5iii**, **ix**, **xiii** (R = 4-Cl, 4-NO₂, 3,4-(Cl)₂) showed excellent activity against Gram-positive bacteria *S. pyogenes* when compared with standard drugs ampicillin. Other compounds showed moderate to poor activity compared with standard drugs gentamycin, chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin.

Antifungal activity :

Good activity was observed for compound **5xiv** (R = 2,5-(Cl)₂) against fungi *C. albicans* and *A. niger* while

rest of the compounds showed moderate to poor activity compared with standard drugs nystatin and greseofulvin.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC. IR absorption spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer RX-1 FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr pellet and ^1H NMR spectra was recorded on

Bruker Avance II in CDCl_3 at 400 MHz.

The compound 2-[2-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4(3H)one **3** was prepared from 2-[(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenyl acetic acid **1** by reported method^{24,25} and the intermediate 2-chloro-*N*-(substituted phenyl)acetamide **i-xv** were also prepared by reported method²⁶. The physical properties are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Characterization data of compounds

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :		
					Found (Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
i	2-Cl	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NOCl}_2$	76	53	47.02 (47.09)	3.42 (3.46)	6.81 (6.86)
ii	3-Cl	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NOCl}_2$	83	52	47.02 (47.09)	3.42 (3.46)	6.81 (6.86)
iii	4-Cl	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NOCl}_2$	73	48	47.02 (47.09)	3.42 (3.46)	6.81 (6.86)
iv	2- CH_3	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{NOCl}$	68	56	58.81 (58.86)	5.46 (5.49)	7.59 (7.63)
v	3- CH_3	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{NOCl}$	80	54	58.81 (58.86)	5.46 (5.49)	7.59 (7.63)
vi	4- CH_3	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{NOCl}$	78	60	58.81 (58.86)	5.46 (5.49)	7.59 (7.63)
vii	2- NO_2	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	64	51	44.71 (44.77)	3.27 (3.29)	13.01 (13.05)
viii	3- NO_2	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	69	58	44.71 (44.77)	3.27 (3.29)	13.01 (13.05)
ix	4- NO_2	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$	73	53	44.71 (44.77)	3.27 (3.29)	13.01 (13.05)
x	4- OCH_3	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_2\text{Cl}$	84	57	54.07 (54.15)	5.02 (5.05)	6.08 (7.02)
xi	2- NO_2 , 4-Cl	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$	77	59	38.52 (38.58)	2.41 (2.43)	11.21 (11.25)
xii	2-Cl, 4- NO_2	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_2$	67	54	38.52 (38.58)	2.41 (2.43)	11.21 (11.25)
xiii	3,4-(Cl) $_2$	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{NOCl}_3$	72	63	40.23 (40.29)	2.52 (2.54)	5.82 (5.87)
xiv	2,5-(Cl) $_2$	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{NOCl}_3$	70	61	40.23 (40.29)	2.52 (2.54)	5.82 (5.87)
xv	H	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{NOCl}$	74	52	56.57 (56.65)	4.72 (4.75)	8.20 (8.26)
5_i	2-Cl	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{19}\text{BrCl}_3\text{N}_5\text{OS}$	94	51	52.63 (52.69)	2.74 (2.80)	10.16 (10.24)
5_{ii}	3-Cl	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{19}\text{BrCl}_3\text{N}_5\text{OS}$	82	56	52.63 (52.69)	2.74 (2.80)	10.16 (10.24)

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

5 _{iii}	4-Cl	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ BrCl ₃ N ₅ OS	91	63	52.63 (52.69)	2.74 (2.80)	10.16 (10.24)
5 _{iv}	2-CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ BrCl ₂ N ₅ OS	121	52	56.05 (56.12)	3.29 (3.34)	11.51 (10.56)
5 _v	3-CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ BrCl ₂ N ₅ OS	119	57	56.05 (56.12)	3.29 (3.34)	11.51 (10.56)
5 _{vi}	4-CH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ BrCl ₂ N ₅ OS	103	51	56.05 (56.12)	3.29 (3.34)	11.51 (10.56)
5 _{vii}	2-NO ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ BrCl ₂ N ₆ O ₃ S	102	46	51.83 (51.89)	2.68 (2.76)	12.04 (12.10)
5 _{viii}	3-NO ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ BrCl ₂ N ₆ O ₃ S	113	53	51.83 (51.89)	2.68 (2.76)	12.04 (12.10)
5 _{ix}	4-NO ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ BrCl ₂ N ₆ O ₃ S	95	59	51.83 (51.89)	2.68 (2.76)	12.04 (12.10)
5 _x	4-OCH ₃	C ₃₁ H ₂₂ BrCl ₂ N ₅ O ₂ S	118	57	54.76 (54.80)	3.21 (3.26)	10.26 (10.31)
5 _{xi}	2-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ BrCl ₃ N ₆ O ₃ S	104	49	49.39 (49.44)	2.43 (2.49)	11.47 (11.53)
5 _{xii}	2-Cl, 4-NO ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ BrCl ₃ N ₆ O ₃ S	100	65	49.39 (49.44)	2.43 (2.49)	11.47 (11.53)
5 _{xiii}	3,4-(Cl) ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ BrCl ₄ N ₅ OS	81	58	50.12 (50.16)	2.47 (2.53)	9.71 (9.75)
5 _{xiv}	2,5-(Cl) ₂	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ BrCl ₄ N ₅ OS	92	52	50.12 (50.16)	2.47 (2.53)	9.71 (9.75)
5 _{xv}	H	C ₃₀ H ₂₀ BrCl ₂ N ₅ OS	118	55	55.41 (55.49)	3.02 (3.10)	10.73 (10.78)

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activity data

Compd.	Minimal bactericidal concentration (µg/ml)				Minimal fungicidal concentration (µg/ml)		
	Gram-negative		Gram-positive		<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. clavatus</i>
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>			
i	500	1000	250	250	1000	1000	> 1000
ii	250	500	500	1000	1000	1000	> 1000
iii	250	1000	250	250	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
iv	100	200	250	250	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
v	100	250	500	500	500	500	> 1000
vi	500	500	100	100	1000	500	> 1000
vii	500	1000	500	250	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
viii	50	100	200	200	500	500	500
ix	250	500	1000	1000	500	> 1000	> 1000
x	500	500	1000	1000	500	> 1000	> 1000
xi	500	1000	250	500	1000	1000	> 1000
xii	500	500	500	1000	1000	1000	> 1000
xiii	250	500	500	1000	> 1000	> 1000	500
xiv	125	250	100	250	500	> 1000	> 1000
xv	250	500	250	250	500	> 1000	> 1000

Table-2 (contd.)

S _i	500	500	500	500	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
S _{ii}	100	500	1000	500	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
S _{iii}	500	1000	1000	100	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
S _{iv}	500	500	100	1000	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
S _v	500	200	500	500	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
S _{vi}	250	500	1000	500	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
S _{vii}	250	500	500	1000	1000	1000	1000
S _{viii}	50	100	500	1000	1000	1000	1000
S _{ix}	50	200	500	100	1000	1000	1000
S _x	500	100	100	1000	> 1000	> 1000	> 1000
S _{xi}	100	200	500	500	1000	1000	1000
S _{xii}	50	100	500	200	500	1000	1000
S _{xiii}	50	200	1000	100	500	1000	1000
S _{xiv}	100	500	100	200	200	500	1000
S _{xv}	100	500	500	1000	500	1000	1000
Gentamycin	0.05	1	0.25	0.5	-	-	-
Ampicillin	100	100	250	100	-	-	-
Chloramphenicol	50	50	50	50	-	-	-
Ciprofloxacin	25	25	50	50	-	-	-
Norfloxacin	10	10	10	10	-	-	-
Nystatin	-	-	-	-	100	100	100
Greseofulvin	-	-	-	-	500	100	100

2-[2-(2,6-Dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-6-bromo-3,1-benzoxazin-4(3H)one²⁶ (3) :

Yield 51%, m.p. 198 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3450 (NH), 2957, 2925 (C-H), 1687 (C=O), 1614 (C=N), 1320 (C-N), 1156 (C-O-C), 787 (C-Cl), 750 (NH wag), 642 (C-Br); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 9.36 (1H, s, NH), 6.38–7.68 (10H, m, Ar-H), 3.74 (2H, s, CH₂).

2-[2-(2,6-Dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-3-thiocarboxamide-6-bromoquinazolin-4(3H)ones²⁷ (4) :

A mixture of 2-[2-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-6-bromo-3,1-benzoxazin-4(3H)one 3 (2.38 g, 0.005 mol) and thiourea (0.38 g, 0.005 mol) in pyridine were heated on oil bath at 180–200 °C for 5–6 h. After completion, the reaction mixture was poured into ice cold water containing conc. HCl. The separated solid was filtered, washed and recrystallized from ethanol.

Yield 48%, m.p. 162 °C; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3506, 3470 (NH₂), 3385 (NH), 2952, 2910 (C-H), 1693 (C=O), 1611 (C=N), 1307 (C=S), 1320 (C-N), 788 (C-Cl), 750 (NH wag); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 9.18 (1H, s, NH), 6.39–7.50 (10H, m, Ar-H), 4.88 (2H, s, NH₂), 3.77 (2H, s, CH₂).

2-[2-(2,6-Dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-3-{4-[4-methoxyphenyl)amino]-1,3-thiazol-2-yl}-6-bromoquinazolin-4(3H)one²⁸ (5x) :

2-Chloro-N-(4-methoxyphenyl)acetamide x (0.99 g, 0.005 mol) and 2-[2-(2,6-dichlorophenyl)amino]phenylmethyl-3-thiocarboxamide-6-bromoquinazolin-4(3H)one 4 (2.67 g, 0.005 mol) in ethanol was refluxed for 6 h and allowed to stand undisturbed overnight. The solid, which was separated on cooling, filtered and recrystallized from a mixture of ethanol and DMF (5–10% of DMF in ethanol).

Yield 57%, m.p. 118 °C (Found : C, 54.76; H, 3.21; N, 10.26. Calcd. for C₃₁H₂₂BrCl₂N₅O₂S : C, 54.80; H, 3.26; N, 10.31%); IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3450 (NH), 2950, 2895 (C-H), 1690 (C=O), 1605 (C=N), 1310 (C-N), 785 (C-Cl), 670 (C-S-C), 625 (C-Br); ¹H NMR (δ ppm) : 3.46 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.78 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.18 (1H, s, CH-S), 8.25 (1H, s, NH-(Th-Ar)), 9.25 (1H, s, NH), 6.39–7.56 (17H, m, Ar-H).

Similarly other thiazole derivatives have been prepared by the same method. Their physical properties and antimicrobial activity are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Note

Scheme

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